

Integration Of National Music Elements Into Piano Education

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18028827>

Annotation: This article analyzes the theoretical and practical foundations of integrating national music elements in the process of piano education. The study covers the issues of applying the tone-tone system, rhythmic structures, maqoms and intonation features of folk melodies, characteristic of the Uzbek national musical heritage, to piano performance and teaching methodology. It also substantiates the pedagogical possibilities of an integrative approach in forming national musical thinking, developing students' artistic and aesthetic taste, and enriching their performance competencies.

Keywords: national music, piano education, integration, folk melodies, musical thinking, performance competence, pedagogical approach, musical heritage.

Introduction.

Music is an artistic expression of the people's psyche, historical memory, and aesthetic thinking. The musical heritage of each nation reflects its spiritual world, worldview and continuity between generations. In the current era of accelerating globalization, music education is faced with the task of not only training professional performers, but also educating a well-rounded individual who understands national identity and approaches musical heritage with respect.

Although piano education has traditionally been formed on the basis of European musical thought, harmonic and polyphonic systems, in today's educational process the need to enrich it with elements of national music is becoming increasingly urgent. Because the piano is an instrument capable of expressing the melodies, rhythmic complexity and intonational diversity inherent in national music with its timbre possibilities, polyphonic power and technical flexibility. It is this aspect that expands the possibilities of integrating piano education with national music.

The introduction of elements of national music into piano education, first of all, serves to form the national foundations of musical thinking in pupils and students. The melodic nature of folk melodies, the tones and methods inherent in the maqom system, along with the development of performing skills in piano lessons, also deepen the ability to feel, interpret and artistically perceive music. This ensures education aimed at understanding and performing music not only technically, but also in terms of content.

From this point of view, the issue of integrating elements of national music into piano education is an important scientific problem not only from the point of view of musicology, but also from the point of view of pedagogy. This process allows developing performing competencies, forming artistic and aesthetic taste, and

enriching the content of education based on national values. As a result, piano education can go beyond its traditional academic boundaries and become a modern educational model that combines national and universal musical values.

The issue of integrating elements of national music into piano education requires, first of all, a theoretical reconsideration of such components as structural units of the musical language: *lad* (tone system), intonation, rhythm-method, texture, harmony, and form. Because while piano performance has historically developed based on European academic traditions, Uzbek national music is characterized by more monodic thinking, intonational development, microintonation, rhythmicity based on method, and oral-professional tradition. The theoretical foundations of the integration process begin with identifying the points of coordination of these two systems.

In the Uzbek national musical heritage, the pitch-tone system is often expressed through *maqom* paths, branches, and stable intonational cores in folk melodies. In this system, the “center” of the melody (base notes), “direction” (the trajectory of the rise and fall of the melody), and “melodic memory” (intonational formula) play an important role. Since the sounds on the piano are located in a tempered (equal distribution) system, the microintonational subtleties inherent in national music (for example, small deviations between notes in the performance of the melody, “slips”) are not directly repeated. For this reason, the following theoretical solutions are highlighted in the integration:

Providing microintonation through an “intonational equivalent”: since there are clear semitones on the piano keyboard, microdeviations are “felt” in the performance with the effects of *appoggiatura*, *mordent*, *gruppetto*, *glissando*, as well as the *legato–non legato* contrast.

Separation of supporting chords to preserve the tone: the chords (basis) that are important in the melody are reinforced in the piano texture by a pedal point in the bass, or an *ostinato* support.

Adapting melodic phrasing to national breath: the phrase in *maqom* and folk melodies is based on “breath”; on the piano, this is formed through *agogy* (natural shift in speed), dynamic wave, articulation. As a result, the national tone features are not “fully copied” on the piano, but are interpreted on the basis of didactic and artistic adaptation.

The main strength of national melodies is in their intonational core. This core is often repeated and developed as a short motif or melodic turn. In theoretical analysis, it is this component that serves as the most effective means of integration, because: the student feels the “spirit” of the melody faster precisely through the intonational formula; motifs become natural training material for developing piano technique (*legato*, *staccato*, *trill*, *passage*); variational development and improvisational elements can be taught through intonation motifs.

Therefore, in the process of theoretical analysis, a basic motif (formula) is extracted from a melody or maqom; its metric-rhythmic model is determined; a “didactic form” is created that is suitable for the piano texture (simple melodic statement → two-voice statement → chordal/harmonic-based statement → variational development). This approach allows the introduction of national material in piano education not as an “additional”, but as thematic and systematic educational content.

Rhythm-method system: the connection of national rhythmic patterns with piano technique. In Uzbek national music, rhythm is a broader concept than simple metric counting and is often manifested as a method (stable rhythmic pattern). In folk melodies, such movement characteristics as “playfulness”, “vibration”, “stepping” are expressed in rhythm. Teaching the method in piano education provides the following theoretical and pedagogical opportunities: coordination: harmony of the right hand melody and the left hand method-ostinato; steady pulse: working with a metronome, internal metric intuition; syncope and stress system: the natural arrangement of national stresses; articulatory precision: expressing the character of the “circle” through staccato/tenuto. Through this, the national method becomes a means of technical training and artistic interpretation at the same time on the piano.

Discussion.

The process of integrating elements of national music into piano education requires, first of all, a re-understanding of the attitude towards music. Because this process is not limited to playing national melodies on one instrument, but is based on the integration of musical thinking, performance culture and aesthetic views. The piano is by its nature an academic, polyphonic, and harmonic product of thought, while folk music is characterized by more monodic development, intonational subtlety, and rhythmic movement based on method. The meeting of these two worlds forms the central point of the discussion.

When approaching the issue of integration, the first question that arises is “to what extent can national music be preserved on the piano?” The fact is that the tempered sound system of the piano does not allow for the full reproduction of the microintonations characteristic of national music. However, this is not to deny integration, but rather to demonstrate the need to implement it on the basis of new artistic solutions. The national melody is “felt” on the piano not through the pitch of the sound, but through intonation mood, phrasing, agogy and articulation. So, the main issue here is not to convey the notes, but the spirit of the melody. The issue of rhythm and method also requires a separate discussion in the integration process. In national music, rhythm is often manifested not as mechanical counting, but as movement, vibration and internal pulse. In piano education, rhythm is often taught from the point of view of technical discipline. The introduction of national methods into piano lessons brings these two approaches closer together: the technique is saturated with musical

content, and the rhythm acquires a lively character. For the student, the ostinato in the left hand becomes not only a technical exercise, but also a support that determines the character of the melody.

The issue of texture and harmony also plays an important role in the discussion. Excessive harmonic enrichment in adapting national melodies to the capabilities of the piano can change the nature of the melody. At the same time, being limited to only one-voice performance does not fully utilize the capabilities of piano education. Therefore, the most optimal way is to find a balance. Methods such as pedal point, modal colors, heterophonic interpretation serve to enrich the piano texture while preserving the essence of the national melody. In this process, harmony does not dominate, but acts as a servant.

Conclusion.

The integration of elements of national music into piano education is not only technical and theoretical, but also has a deep educational value. Working with national melodies broadens the student's musical outlook, connects him with his cultural roots. Referring to a national melody during the lesson turns the performance from just an exercise into an artistic experience. The student begins to perceive music not as “playing”, but as “telling”, “telling a story”. This leads to an increase in emotionality and content in piano performance. At the same time, the integration process also presents certain difficulties. Factors such as the difficulty of notating melodies related to oral tradition, the risk of mechanical repetition of ornaments, and the teacher’s insufficient knowledge of the characteristics of national music complicate this process. However, it is precisely these problems that encourage the enrichment of piano pedagogy and the search for new methodological approaches. Working with national material requires both creativity and musical sensitivity from the teacher. Integrating elements of national music into piano education is not a denial of traditional academic education, but a way to enrich and deepen it. This process turns piano lessons into a place where national and universal musical values are combined. As a result, piano education, along with technical excellence, becomes an effective pedagogical system that serves to form musical thinking, artistic taste, and cultural awareness.

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